

MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES AND THE READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS AMONG GRADE EIGHT STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Reading is one of the macro skills being developed by educators among learners. This goes with the development of the comprehension skills as an essential aspect in the acquisition of the language. The ability of a person to comprehend what he reads varies based on different factors that include the interest and the type of intelligence he has. Thus, this study focused on identifying the significant relationship between the reading comprehension skill and the Multiple Intelligences of Grade Eight students in Batangas Eastern Colleges. The data for identifying the multiple intelligences of students were gathered through a survey questionnaire while their reading comprehensions skill was measured through a test. Based on the result from the survey questionnaire, most of the students answered often in statements that are related to their multiple intelligences. It is shown in the mean score of 3.52 for Bodily-Kinesthetic; 3.68 for Interpersonal; 3.43 for Intrapersonal; 3.45 for Mathematical Logical; 3.41 for Musical Rhythmic and 3.53 for Verbal Linguistic while a mean score of 3.15 for Naturalistic intelligence means sometimes. The researcher found out that in terms of the level of the reading comprehension skill of the students they need more drills/ exercises to improve. Out of the 50 respondents, 33 or 66% of them failed in Distinguishing Fact from Opinion; 19 or 38% in Interpreting Graphs and Making Inferences; and 16 or 34% in Identifying the Main Idea. In relation to the correlation of the multiple intelligences and the reading comprehension skills of the students, it revealed that there is no significant relationship between the two variables. Therefore, it was concluded that they belong to the average group range since there is no specific multiple intelligence that is dominant among the respondents. Furthermore, it implied that multiple intelligences do not directly affect the reading comprehension skill of a learner thus other factors like the interest and habit of an individual have to be considered in developing the skill for language acquisition.

Keywords: Reading, comprehension, reading comprehension, multiple Intelligences, Philippine Education